

A Study on Digital Marketing and Its Impact on Customers and Small Scale Retailers with Reference to Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

India, as the global research and development hub for Manufacturing, has enhanced more and more with digital marketing. We are in a society driven by digital technology, such is its impact that there are countries where citizens don't have running water, but own Smartphone. Digital marketing has an incredible influence on people's interactions, work, purchases and life habits. The objectives of this paper is to study the advancements of digital marketing and its influence on Artificial Intelligence, To understand whether digital marketing aims towards profit generation or customers satisfaction and to understand the impact of small scale retailers on digital marketing concerned with Artificial Intelligences. Therefore digital marketing with the help of Artificial Intelligence makes it easy to rope in customers and also in shaping the modern life of the future.

Hence goes the saying... “Good Marketing Makes the Company Look Smart, Great Marketing Makes the Customers Feel Smart”

- Joe Chernov

Keywords: Advancements, Artificial intelligence Globalisation, Small scale retailers, Revenue generation, Customer satisfaction, Modern life.

Introduction

Digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital technology and Artificial Intelligence, mainly on the internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising and any other digital medium.

The rapid dissemination of information and communication technology (ICT) and particularly the massive adoption of the internet in the past decades have boosted the use of E-commerce as a distribution channel. The growing role of E-commerce resulted in unprecedented structural changes in many industries.

These transformations are already generating a major recognition

in the way some products are manufactured, marketed and purchased, as exemplified by the travel and tourism or media industries. Today business to consumer E-commerce represents only a small segment of total retail in most developed countries but it has been showing impressive growth rates even during the recent economic downturn, auguring a rapid expansion in the years to come.

Objectives

- To Study the advancements of Digital Marketing and its influence on Artificial Intelligence.
- To understand Digital Marketing is aiming towards Profit generation or customer satisfaction.
- To understand the impact of small Scale retailers on Digital Marketing concerned with Artificial Intelligence.

Methodology

Primary Data

Primary data is a original data collected by the investigator for the first time, specially for the purpose in mind and it's also called as first hand data.

Primary data had been collected from 30 respondents of different sectors to find out the impact on customer and Small scale retailers from the usage of Digital Marketing.

Information from Journal Article and Website was taken to provide this Information.

Judgement sampling method used to select the respondents.

Statement of Problem

We can see majority of people using Digital Marketing on regular basis which can be used as a positive aspect for creating the Marketing awareness. But, usually the things are differently used.

The Digital Marketing and Artificial intelligence is an obstacle for the growth of small scale retailers.

The researcher, have observed to what extent is the Digital Marketing is worth full for customers as well as small scale retailers.

So the study focuses on how the Digital Marketing solves the above said problem.

Analysis and Interpretation

Is Digital Marketing making the small scale retailers Unemployed ?

Particulars	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Yes	14	48%
No	16	52%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 14 respondents says YES and 16 respondents says NO, Therefore Digital marketing not making small scale retailers unemployed.

Interpretation-From the above analysis 52% of the respondents says that Digital marketing is not making the small scale retailers unemployed. Hence we can conclude that Digital Marketing is not curbing the employment of Small scale retailers.

Do you think Digital Marketing, always provides you with the quality and hygienic products ?

No of Respondents

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Always	3	10%
Somtimes Yes	18	60%
Never	0	0%
Almost	9	30%
100%	100%	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 9 respondents have said that Digital marketing is providing Quality and Hygienic products whereas 18 respondents says Sometimes YES and 3 completely Agree.

Interpretation-As per the above analysis 60% of the respondents says that Digital marketing provide Quality and Hygienic products, Hence we can conclude that Digital Marketing sometimes provide Quality and Hygienic products.

Is it secured for the customers to shop online ?

Particulars	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Yes	19	63%
No	11	37%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 11 respondents say it is not secured to shop online and rest 19 says its secured.

Interpretation- From the above analysis 63% of the respondents agree about the secureness of the customers to shop online. Therefore to conclude we can say that it is secured for the customers to shop online.

Customers are getting attracted for Digital Marketing only due to its Lavishness

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
True	13	43.30%
False	17	56.70%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 17 respondents disagree that the customers are getting attracted for digital marketing due to its Lavishness and the rest 13 agrees that they are getting attracted.

Interpretation- From the above analysis 56.70% of the respondents says that the customers are not attracted for digital marketing due to its Lavishness. Therefore to conclude we can say that Customers are not attracted for digital marketing due to its Lavishness.

Digital Marketing mainly has Profit motive ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Yes	8	26.70%
No	22	73.30%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 22 respondents disagree that Digital marketing mainly has profit motive and the rest 8 respondents agrees that it mainly has profit motive.

Interpretation- As per the survey 73.30% of the respondents say that Digital marketing does not mainly focus on profit motive. Hence to conclude we can say that the aim or motive of the Digital marketing is not only to earn profit but also providing a better service for its customers.

Is Digital marketing is boon or bane to the customers ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Boon	24	80%
Bane	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 24 respondents say that digital marketing is Boon for the customers and the rest 6 say that it is Bane.

Interpretation- As per the survey analysis 80% of the respondents says that Digital Marketing is Boon for the customers. Therefore we can say that Digital marketing is Boon for the customers rather than being Bane.

“ If your business is not on the internet, Then your business will be out of business” Do you agree with the above Quote ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Strongly Agree	6	20%
Agree	5	46.70%
Natural	14	46.70%
Disagree	5	16.70%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- From the above chart 14 respondents says that the Quote is Neutral, 6 respondents strongly agree the Quote, 5 agree and another 5 disagree the Quote.

Interpretation- From the above analysis 46.70% of the respondents say that the quote may be or may not be true. Therefore to conclude we can say that the Quote is Neutral.

Do you think that the customers are manipulated from Digital marketing ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Yes	24	80%
No	6	20%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- The above chart say that 24 respondents agree that the customers are manipulated from Digital Marketing and the rest 6 says No.

Interpretation- From the above analysis 80% of the respondents says that the customers are manipulated from the Digital Marketing. Therefore to conclude we can say that the customers are manipulated from Digital marketing.

What does a retailer focus on, while operating in Digital marketing ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Profit	5	16.70%
Customer Satisfaction	7	23.30%
Maximize Sales	7	23.30%
Expansopm and Modernization	11	36.70%
Total	30	100%

Analysis- The above chart shows that 11respondents say that the retailer focuses only on Expansion and modernization, 7 respondents says that he focuses on profit, another 7 says that he focus on customer satisfaction and the rest 5 says that he focus only on Profit.

Interpretation- From the survey analysis we can say that the retailer focuses on Expansion and Modernization.

Is success rate of the Brands depends on digital marketing ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Yes	6	20%
No	24	80%
Total	30	100%

Analysis-The above chart shows that 24 respondents says disagree that the success rate of brands depends on Digital Marketing and rest 6 respondents agree that the success rate of brands depends on the Digital Marketing.

Interpretation- From the survey analysis we can find that 80% of the respondents disagree that the success rate of the brands depends on the digital marketing. Hence to conclude we can say that the success rate of the brands does not depend upon the Digital Marketing.

Findings

From the above conducted survey, we have found the following

- Digital marketing which is enclosed with Artificial Intelligence has lot of advantages and it's a boon to the society.
- Today's customer feel secured to shop online.
- We can say that digital marketing sometimes provides quality and hygienic products, but not always.
- Artificial Intelligence mainly has profit motive.
- Digital marketing is not curbing the employment of small scale retailers.
- Customers are getting are getting attracted for digital marketing due to its lavishness.
- In majority of times customers are manipulated from Artificial Intelligence.
- Retailers focus on expansion and modernisation in digital marketing.
- The success rate of the products and their brands depends on influence of Artificial Intelligence with digital marketing.

Suggestions

- Even though there are various advantages and disadvantages from digital marketing, today's generation feels that it's a boon to society and must be used efficiently.
- Like any other business digital marketing is also a profit oriental business, it is Making customers getting attracted through various forms .But it's not thinking customer's satisfaction.
- Digital marketing may not curve the employment of small scale retailers directly but through the aspect of focusing on expansion and modernisation .Its making their survival difficult.

Conclusions

Digital marketing has an incredible influence on people's interaction, work, purchases and life habits. The objective of our paper was to study the advancement of digital marketing and its impact on customers as well as small scale retailers. We had conducted the survey from 30 respondents, where we found majority of them agree that the digital marketing is worthfull for customers and helpful for the economy. Hence to conclude we can say that "Good marketing makes company look smart....Great marketing makes the customer feel smart."

Web Sources

<https://en.m.wikibooks.org>

<https://blog.hubspot.com>

<https://www.myaccountingcourse.com>

https://www.sas.com/sas/offers/18/multichannel-marketing-attribution-106973.html?gclid=EAlalQobChMlr9bMsdji3AlVwxmpCh3lKwnbEAAYAiAAYAEgkl_D_BwE

Newspapers and magazines

Journals